

An overview of nucleosynthesis and Cosmological parameters and observations using CMB and redshift

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ABSTRACT

The Big Bang nucleosynthesis has some elements in it which are of utmost importance to understand how the Universe is as we know it. From the Planck epoch to the stellar evolution era when the first stellar nucleosynthesis took place, our two main weapons have been CMB and the Hubble (and therefore redshift) measurements. Our consideration in this paper will primarily be on the QCD transition phase, when the behaviour of matter (quarks, gluons) was quite important in the structure of the Big Bang model. Then, we will consider the Baryon asymmetry problem, where we will discuss the inequality of matter and anti-matter. We will also briefly discuss the synthesis of Baryons and leptons, the Sakharov outlines and the Baryon number, and its conditions with the outline under Thermodynamic equilibrium departure and the C-CP symmetry violation conditions. We will then consider how there is a difference between the predicted and observed values of the various important values, here the abundance of ${}^6\text{Lithium}$ and the Hubble parameter, where data from the 2015 *Planck* project shows inequalities between predicted and measured redshift values and then consider some additional points.

1.1: The grand picture of Cosmological inflation

The Big Bang took place at “ $t=0$ ” on the Cosmic timescale. With each progressing second, many key events took place. One second after the Big Bang, neutrino decoupling took place. But, even within that one second, many other events had structures themselves. Less than 10^{-35} seconds after the Big bang, the forces of the Standard Model had been unified, but, just less than 10^{-32} seconds after the Big

Bang, the strong nuclear force had separated from the Grand Unification era, while the temperature decreased by a factor of 10^5 , while less than 10^{-15} seconds after the Big Bang, the entire GUT epoch has ended, and the formation of *Quark Gluon Plasma* takes place. Eventually, the elementary *nucleosynthesis* starts at somewhere around 10^1 seconds, where the first protons fused with neutrons to form the first hydrogen in the Universe, along with traces of deuterium. Further, as Baryonsynthesis progresses, there happens a difference in the ratio of matter to anti-matter. Meanwhile, as leptons and

anti-leptons annihilate in the leptonic era, photons are produced for the first time in the infant Universe. At this time period, from around 10 seconds after the Big Bang, the Universe is full of plasma. The QCD transition phase is thought to have taken place 10^{-5} seconds after the Big Bang, along with the electroweak transition phase at around 300 GeV, at around 10^{-11} seconds after the Big Bang. Further, as time progressed, the present Standard Model formed, as the temperatures eventually cooled down during the inflationary period. By then, the Weak nuclear force split from the unified *gauge* force (the combined Electroweak force and the Strong nuclear force), while the Gravitational force split from the entire unification. The “less than Planck” epoch is thought to have been until 10^{-43} seconds after the Big Bang. 10^{-37} seconds after the Big Bang, there is the era when the electroweak and the strong nuclear forces are thought to have been united. 10^{-6} seconds after the Big Bang, quarks cooled from QGP to form baryons, and it is at this time that Baryon asymmetry arose, and by then the QCD transition epoch was underway. By 10^1 seconds after the Big Bang, the majority of hadrons annihilated with antihadrons, leaving the Universe a soup of leptons and due to the high energy and temperatures, electron-positron pairs stayed in thermal equilibrium. Gradually, the inflation allowed cooling of the Universe, and neutrino decoupling took place. At this point, electron-positron pairs annihilated. Around from 10^1 seconds, the Big Bang nucleosynthesis took place, leading to the formation of the first light hydrogen (protium) and He-4, along with traces of deuterium, and other isotopes of helium. From 10^1 seconds to 10^{13} seconds after the Big Bang, the Universe, it is a

sphere of plasma, radiation, and electrons with a comparatively lesser traces of nuclei. Eventually, *recombination* took place, where the thermal dynamics of the Universe was favourable for electrons to become electrostatically bound to a nucleus. The present day CMB originated at this time, and the photons of CMB redshifted after this period ended.

The first stars formed after the dark ages ended, when there was only the stretched spectral hydrogen radio waves.

Our interest will be in mapping QCD transition, which is taken to be a very important point which decides the Baryon asymmetric nature of the Universe.

1.2: QCD transition phase

The QCD transition is quite similar to that of a chemical compound. At certain temperatures, Quarks were not confined, but after cooling a certain temperature limit, they were bound to form confined structures. The QCD transition took place at around 10^{-5} seconds after the Big Bang. This result holds from the Friedmann equations. The Friedmann equations show that the scale factor follows

$$a \propto e^{\pm Ht}$$

And further proposes that the scale factor can predict the temperature. For QCD transition, a very important result is that following from the real-Hubble time relation for a radiation dominated Universe,

$$t_{Hubble} = \frac{t}{3}$$

We see that from the Friedmann equation,

$$H^2 = \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G\rho}{3}$$

The temperature at QCD transition is taken as 150 MeV, and therefore by comparing the relativistic degree of freedom, we can show that the time after which QCD transition took place is 10^{-5} seconds. Until then, the Quarks were free, but after that they “solidified”, as you can term them similar to a chemical phase transition, such as that of water. The inflation of the Universe is also an important key to understanding the possible behaviour of matter less than about 10^{-6} seconds after the Big Bang. The inflation is also a very important point. Under the Cosmological principle, we see that the Universe is considered to be *homogeneous* and *isotropic*, and we can easily write out the FLRW metric as

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + a^2(t)\{dS + d\Omega^2\}$$

Where dS is defined as:

$$dS = \frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2}$$

Where $k = -1, 0,$ or $+1$ depending on whether the Universe is considered to be negatively curved (H^3), flat (R^3) or positively curved (S^3). The data from the Supernova-Cosmology experiment shows using Type IA supernovae as “Standard Candles” that the Universe is accelerating, i.e. $H > 0$, which we will use in the following paragraphs.

Given the Energy-Momentum-Density Tensor is defined as

$$T_\nu^\mu = \text{diag}(-\rho, p, p, p)$$

Has only two *truly independent* components, that of $\mu = \nu = 0$, and that

of $\mu = \nu = i$. So, from the Field equation in General Relativity,

$$G_{\mu\nu} + g_{\mu\nu}\Lambda = 8\pi GT_{\mu\nu}$$

Where we define the Einstein Tensor as

$$G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R$$

And so we can easily determine the respective components of the metric, and therefore the value of $G_{\mu\nu}$.

We see that the FLRW equations reduce to two equations of the form,

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 &= \frac{8\pi G}{3}\rho - \frac{k}{a^2} + \frac{\Lambda}{3} \\ 2\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} + \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 &= (-1)8\pi G\rho - \frac{k}{a^2} + \Lambda \end{aligned}$$

Finally, from the equation of state, relating ρ and p as

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = (-1)4\pi G(\rho + 3p) + \frac{\Lambda}{3}$$

This result is a key which opens up the inflationary model, and following the Supernova Cosmology project, we have deduced this equation (here we are considering a flat Universe, or $k = 0$).

Further, for inflation we can consider a scalar field $\psi(t)$, and write out the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho &= \frac{1}{2}\dot{\psi}(t) + V(\psi) \\ p &= \frac{1}{2}\dot{\psi}(t) - V(\psi) \end{aligned}$$

This (real) scalar field $\psi(t)$ finds its roles in quintessence, also as a possible inflaton. The inflationary model offers the transition a very huge reasoning to both, the electroweak and the QCD transition.

QCD transition also has its implications in Baryon asymmetry, which we will discuss in the next section.

2.1: The Baryon asymmetry and the Sakharov outline

There is a fine distinction between the number of Baryons and anti-Baryons, and there arises the question, “what lead to such an inequality in a Universe which started with the same ratios of particles?” In order to explain these, the *Sakharov* outline labelled the following three possibilities, each of which are closing to be proved:

1. There must have happened a physical event that caused a change, or a *departure* from thermal equilibrium,
2. There must be a form of violation of the (C) CP symmetry violation, as a Universe with symmetry would mean invariance under CP symmetry¹, or
3. A violation of the Baryon number conservation.

The essence of these conditions arise from the Baryon number (one-third the difference of the number of quarks to that of anti-quarks), which is conserved in the Big Bang, meaning that there must have happened an event *after* the Big Bang that caused one of the above conditions to

¹ CP symmetry violation is not described in the usual Standard Model, and a solution is provided by possible extensions of it. It is compatible and can explain in its usual range the first Sakharov condition.

change and produce an asymmetry in the number of Baryons to anti-Baryons. As of now, the condition (2) has been shown to exist, from the Fitch-Cronin experiment in 1964, which showed from the Kaon that there exists a form of violation of CP symmetry. Also, there is the importance of SUSY in understanding Baryonsynthesis, and there are certain implications in understanding Baryon asymmetry. Besides these, we also have the Affleck-Dine mechanism, where the SUSY shows that quarks and leptons are equipped with scalar fields that correspond to the Baryon and Lepton numbers respectively, and this idea eventually leads into CP symmetry violation. Along with these mechanisms, we also have certain important ideas, like the *B-L* mechanism, which also is important in explaining these mechanisms. It considers the difference between the Baryon number and the Lepton number. Also, through the Affleck-Dine mechanism, the taking is such that we can show the Lagrangian of the Scalar field violates CP symmetry, where the Scalar field in consideration has a non-zero Baryon number. As discussed along-side the Affleck-Dine mechanism, SUSY is important both for CDM² (Cold Dark Matter) candidates and in the consideration of violations of the CP symmetry, thereby satisfying a very crucial stage in the entire Sakharov outline.

In the aftermath of the Big Bang nucleosynthesis, there arises many topics which need to be addressed, while some has quite straight-forward solutions. For

² Light SUSY particles are thought to be some of the important candidates in consideration for possible CDM particles.

example, the formal predictions of the Baryonic density from the Big Bang nucleosynthesis. This can be achieved simply by considering CMB temperature changes. An example of an important mechanism to be understood is the synthesis of Lithium, where data from nuclear stellar observations show a small difference between theoretical and the observed values of the Li/H ratios. An elegant possibility arises with SUSY, where SUSY decays give rise to the possibility to produce ${}^6\text{Li}$ or take away ${}^7\text{Li}$, and thereby giving rise to a solution to the Lithium problem. Another quite interesting problem is to determine whether the amount of ${}^3\text{He}$ has increased or decreased during the Stellar evolution period. The parameter η defined as the ratio of the amount of Baryons to that of Photons $\frac{n_B}{n_\gamma}$. In fact, we can determine the abundance of *light* elements. For instance, Deuterium has been found to have an abundance measurement of $\approx 2.8 \times 10^{-5}$. Further, ${}^7\text{Li}$ has been taken³ to have an abundance of $\approx 6.15 \times 10^{-10}$. The abundance is measured at a factor 10^{-10} relative to the Hydrogen.

An important parameter in the determination of temperature and radiation energy density relation is the *redshift*, which we will discuss in the next section.

2.2: Cosmological redshift inequality with observations

³ The measurement is taken as an *upper bound*, as the usual measurement method of observing metal-poor halo stars is only so much accurate, and this has to do with the Lithium at the surface, and so after the consideration of possible *allowed*

Measurements of the (commoving) distance of an object in an FLRW Universe can be done by first expressing the Hubble scale as a function of redshift, z and the consideration of the “present day” scale factor, depicted as a_0 via the commoving coordinate χ , via the following equation:

$$a_0\chi(\bar{z}) = c \int_0^{\bar{z}} \frac{dz}{H(z)}$$

Here, the values do not consider any additional redshifts arising from individual additions of galactic redshifts.

We have many methods of measuring the redshift using stellar systems, such as Cepheid variables, Type IA Supernovae, RR Lyrae stars, eclipsing binary stars, Tonry-Schneider surface fluctuations method, Tully-Fisher relation, and many other stellar systems that exhibit periodic luminous pulses (In fact, pulsars have also been used for their regular spins, which can be used to find the redshift too).

A primary problem arising with mismatches from theoretical and observational measurements is that of the redshifts predicted by the Hubble constant relations and that of the *Planck* data, from observations from Type IA Supernovae. This turns to be inconsistent with the predicted amount from the CMB and the BAO measurements. From data from *Cepheid* stars⁴ the value of the Hubble constant is different from that of the *Planck* by a difference of $\sim 5.52 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$.

uncertainty bounds, we reach to the number specified above in the text.

⁴ Cepheid stars have a periodic regular luminous pulsating nature, which categorizes them as ideal *Standard Candles*, along with Type IA Supernovae, which have a similar nature

A similar problem arises with the equation mentioned above, where we have considered the redshift in consideration to be the one arising from the expansion of the Universe, and not from any additions of Galactic redshift, as mentioned in the text. It is very simple to add an extra term compensating for this difference, which can be done by considering the usual Cosmological redshift, and by taking in the probable error sources and adding the Galactic redshift. Such would be very simple to write out if considered in terms of the *geocentric* redshift.

$$(1 + \bar{z})(1 + z_a)(1 + z_a^g)(1 + z_\varphi)(1 + z_\varphi^g)$$

Here, z_a refers to the changed additional velocity term, z_a^g refers to the additional velocity term of the galaxy, while z_φ^g is the individual gravitational redshift by the galaxy, labelled "peculiar". This is also a very key factor in determining measurements and observables in Cosmology, and the individual density-expansion parameters can be easily deduced. As considered above, there are differences in the observed values of these, and there is the need for these to be considered.

Although there are many variations and points that lead from this, there still remains "why the inconsistency" between the predicted and observed values. From the usual Friedmann equation, we can define additional parameters in terms of their individual densities as

$$H^2 = H_0^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_\gamma}{a^4} + \frac{\Omega_m}{a^3} + \frac{\Omega_k}{a^2} + \Omega_\Lambda \right)$$

As we have discussed above already, it is quite simple to note down the CMB results show the respective measurements

required for the parameter η and thus relates to individual densities of the ratio of Baryon to that of Photons, and predicts therefore the values of the abundance of light elements, and data from various sources, importantly the *Planck* shows there is an inconsistency, and it still is a very important question to understand the epoch of the Big Bang nucleosynthesis. But, newer suggestions are constantly showing how better models can predict and extend solutions. As seen above, SUSY is a very valuable thought, and therefore has very huge implications in determining possible solutions to the Lithium problem. In general, light SUSY particles could have been housed during the Big Bang nucleosynthesis, and this has many implications to be addressed, and more specifically, SUSY decay could of negative long particles could potentially show a possible solution to the Lithium observation-prediction inconsistency, and thereby can resolve the factors.

Conclusion

We have taken a quick view of the vast landscape of elementary nucleosynthesis, and various parametric relations that are important and are key to solving deeper and vaster questions. We have taken a glimpse of QCD transition, Baryon asymmetry, various mechanisms alongside the Sakharov conditions, and have considered inconsistencies with the theoretical and observed values of Lithium, Hubble scale parameter and also redshift as observed from various sources, and have briefly checked the possible solutions to these questions, such as SUSY decay, and redshift "peculiar" additions.

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